

Centered Triangular Mean Graphs

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Abstract: A graph $G = (V, E)$ with p vertices and q edges is said to have centered triangular mean labeling if it is possible to label the vertices $x \in V$ with distinct elements $f(x)$ from S , where S is a set of non-negative integers in such a way that for each edge $e = uv$, $f^*(e) = \left\lceil \frac{f(u)+f(v)}{2} \right\rceil$ and the resulting edge labels are the first q centered triangular numbers. A graph that admits a centered triangular mean labeling is called centered triangular mean graph. In this paper, we prove that the graphs P_n , $K_{1,n}$, $B_{m,n}$, coconut tree, caterpillar $S(n_1, n_2, n_3, \dots, n_m)$, $St(n_1, n_2, n_3, \dots, n_m)$, $Bt(\underbrace{n, n, \dots, n}_m)$ and $P_m @ P_n$ are centered triangular mean graphs.

Key Words: Mean labeling, Smarandache mean m -labelling, triangular mean labeling, triangular mean graph, centered triangular mean labeling, centered triangular mean graph.

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§1. Introduction

By a graph, we mean a finite, simple and undirected one. The vertex set and the edge set of a graph G are denoted by $V(G)$ and $E(G)$ respectively. For various graph theoretic notations and terminology we follow Harary [2] and for number theory Burton[1]. A graph labeling is an assignment of integers to the vertices or edges or both, subject to certain conditions and a detailed survey on graph labeling is available in [3]. The concept of mean labeling was introduced by Somasundaram et al.[6]. A graph $G = (V, E)$ with p vertices and q edges is called a mean graph if there is an injective function f that maps $V(G)$ to $\{0, 1, 2, \dots, q\}$ such that each edge uv is labeled with $\frac{f(u)+f(v)}{2}$ if $f(u) + f(v)$ is even and $\frac{f(u)+f(v)+1}{2}$ if $f(u) + f(v)$ is odd and the resulting labels of the edges are distinct and are $0, 1, 2, \dots, q$. Generally, if each edge uv is labeled with $\frac{f(u)+f(v)}{m}$ if f maps $V(G)$ to $\{0, 1, 2, \dots, q, 2, 4, \dots, 2q, \dots, m, 2m, 4m \dots, qm\}$ such that $\frac{f(u)+f(v)+m-k}{m}$ if $f(u) + f(v) \equiv k(modm)$ the resulting labels of the edges are distinct and are $0, 1, 2, \dots, q$, such a labeling f is called a *Smarandache mean m -labeling* and G a *Smarandache m -mean graph*, where $m \geq 2$ is an integer. Particularly, a Smarandache 2-mean

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graph is nothing else but a mean graph. Several papers have been published on mean labeling and its variations.

Seenivasan et al.[5] introduced the concept of triangular mean labeling in 2007. A triangular mean labeling of a graph $G = (V, E)$ with p vertices and q edges is an injection $f : V(G) \rightarrow \{0, 1, 2, 3, \dots, T_q\}$ such that for each edge $e = uv$, the edge labels are defined as $f^*(e) = \left\lfloor \frac{f(u)+f(v)}{2} \right\rfloor$ such that the values of the edges are the first q triangular numbers. A graph that admits a triangular mean labeling is called triangular mean graph.

Recently, the number theory has a strong impact on graph theory. A triangular number[1] is a number obtained by adding all positive numbers less than or equal to a given positive integer n . If the n^{th} triangular number[1] is denoted by T_n , then $T_n = \frac{1}{2}n(n + 1)$. A centered triangular number is a centered figurative number that represents a triangle with a dot in the center and all other dots surrounding the center in successive triangular layers. If the n^{th} centered triangular number is denoted by cT_n , then $cT_n = \frac{1}{2}(3n^2 - 3n + 2)$. The first few centered triangular numbers are 1, 4, 10, 19, 31, 46, 64, 85, \dots .

The figurative representations of the first four centered triangular numbers are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1

The notion of centered triangular sum labeling was due to Murugesan et al.[4] in 2013. Motivated by the results in [4] and [5] and using the centered triangular concept in number theory [1] we define a new labeling called centered triangular mean labeling. A graph $G = (V, E)$ with p vertices and q edges is said to have centered triangular mean labeling if it is possible to label the vertices $x \in V$ with distinct elements $f(x)$ from S , where S is a set of non-negative integers such that for each edge $e = uv$, $f^*(e) = \left\lfloor \frac{f(u)+f(v)}{2} \right\rfloor$, and the resulting labels of the edges are the first q centered triangular numbers. A graph that admits a centered triangular mean labeling is called centered triangular mean graph. In this paper, we prove that the graph $P_n, K_{1,n}, B_{m,n}$, coconut tree, caterpillar $S(n_1, n_2, n_3, \dots, n_m), St(n_1, n_2, n_3, \dots, n_m), Bt(\underbrace{n, n, \dots, n}_{m \text{ times}})$ and $P_m @ P_n$ are centered triangular mean graphs. We use the following definitions in the subsequent sequel.

Definition 1.1 The bistar $B_{m,n}$ is a graph obtained from K_2 by joining m pendant edges to one end of K_2 and n pendant edges to the other end of K_2 .

Definition 1.2 A caterpillar is a tree with a path $P_m: v_1, v_2, \dots, v_m$, called spine with leaves(pendant vertices) known as feet attached to the vertices of the spine by edges known as legs. If every spine vertex v_i is attached with n_i number of leaves then the caterpillar is

denoted by $S(n_1, n_2, \dots, n_m)$.

Definition 1.3 The shrub $St(n_1, n_2, \dots, n_m)$ is a graph obtained by connecting a vertex v_0 to central vertex of each of m number of stars.

Definition 1.4 The banana tree $Bt(n_1, n_2, \dots, n_m)$ is a graph obtained by connecting a vertex v_0 to one leaf of each of m number of stars.

Definition 1.5 The graph $P_m @ P_n$ is obtained from P_m and m copies of P_n by identifying one pendant vertex of the i^{th} copy of P_n with i^{th} vertex of P_m where P_m is a path of length of $m - 1$.

§2. Centered Triangular Mean Graphs

Theorem 2.1 The path $P_n (n \geq 1)$ is a centered triangular mean graph.

Proof Let v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n be the vertices of the path P_n . Define $f : V(P_n) \rightarrow S$ as follows:

$$f(v_1) = 0,$$

$$f(v_j) = 2(cT_{j-1} - cT_{j-2} + cT_{j-3} - \dots + (-1)^j cT_1) \text{ for } 2 \leq j \leq n.$$

Let $e_i = v_i v_{i+1} (1 \leq i \leq n - 1)$ be the edges of P_n . For each vertex label f , the induced edge label f^* is defined to be $f^*(e_i) = cT_i$ for $1 \leq i \leq n - 1$. Then f is a centered triangular mean labeling. Hence P_n is a centered triangular mean graph. \square

The centered triangular mean labeling of P_5 is given in Figure 2.

Figure 2

Theorem 2.2 The star graph $K_{1,n} (n \geq 1)$ admits centered triangular mean labeling.

Proof Let v be the apex vertex and let v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n be the pendant vertices of the star $K_{1,n}$. Define $f : V(K_{1,n}) \rightarrow S$ to be $f(v) = 0, f(v_j) = 2cT_j$ for $1 \leq j \leq n$.

For each vertex label f , the induced edge label f^* is defined to be $f^*(vv_j) = cT_j$ for $1 \leq j \leq n$. Then the induced edge labels are the centered triangular numbers $cT_1, cT_2, cT_3, \dots, cT_n$. Hence $K_{1,n}$ is a centered triangular mean graph. \square

The centered triangular mean labeling of $K_{1,8}$ is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3

Theorem 2.3 *The bistar $B_{m,n}$ ($m \geq 1, n \geq 1$) is a centered triangular mean graph.*

Proof Let $V(B_{m,n}) = \{u, v, u_i, v_j : 1 \leq i \leq m, 1 \leq j \leq n\}$ and $E(B_{m,n}) = \{uv, uu_i, vv_j : 1 \leq i \leq m, 1 \leq j \leq n\}$. Define $f : V(B_{m,n}) \rightarrow S$ as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} f(u) &= 0, f(v) = 2, \\ f(u_i) &= 2cT_{i+1} \text{ for } 1 \leq i \leq m, \\ f(v_j) &= 2(cT_{m+j+1} - 1) \text{ for } 1 \leq j \leq n. \end{aligned}$$

For each vertex label f , the induced edge label f^* is defined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} f^*(uv) &= cT_1, \\ f^*(uu_i) &= cT_{i+1} \text{ for } 1 \leq i \leq m, \\ f^*(vv_j) &= cT_{m+j+1} \text{ for } 1 \leq j \leq n. \end{aligned}$$

Then the induced edge labels are the first $m + n + 1$ centered triangular numbers. Hence $B_{m,n}$ is a centered triangular mean graph. \square

The centered triangular labeling of $B_{4,5}$ is given in Figure 4.

Figure 4

Theorem 2.4 *The coconut tree $T(n, m)$, obtained by identifying the central vertex of the star $K_{1,m}$ with a pendant vertex of a path P_n , is a centered triangular mean graph.*

Proof Let $u_0, u_1, u_2, \dots, u_n$ be the vertices of a path, having path length n ($n \geq 1$) and v_1, v_2, \dots, v_m be the pendant vertices being adjacent with u_0 . Define $f : V(T(n, m)) \rightarrow S$ as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} f(u_0) &= 0, \\ f(u_1) &= 2cT_{m+1}, \\ f(v_i) &= 2cT_i \text{ for } 1 \leq i \leq m, \end{aligned}$$

$$f(u_j) = 2(cT_{m+j} - cT_{m+j-1} + cT_{m+j-2} - \dots + (-1)^{j+1}cT_{m+1}) \text{ for } 2 \leq j \leq n.$$

For each vertex label f , the induced edge label f^* is defined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} f^*(u_0v_i) &= cT_i \text{ for } 1 \leq i \leq m, \\ f^*(u_0u_1) &= cT_{m+1}, \\ f^*(u_ju_{j+1}) &= cT_{m+j+1} \text{ for } 1 \leq j \leq n-1. \end{aligned}$$

Then the induced edge labels are the first $m+n$ centered triangular numbers. Hence, coconut tree admits centered triangular mean labeling. \square

The centered triangular mean labeling of $T(3,7)$ is given in Figure 5.

Figure 5

Theorem 2.5 *The caterpillar $S(n_1, n_2, \dots, n_m)$ is a centered triangular mean graph.*

Proof Let v_1, v_2, \dots, v_m be the vertices of the path P_m and $v_i^j (1 \leq i \leq n_j, 1 \leq j \leq m)$ be the pendant vertices joined with $v_j (1 \leq j \leq m)$ by an edge. Then

$$\begin{aligned} V(S(n_1, n_2, \dots, n_m)) &= \{v_j, v_i^j : 1 \leq i \leq n_j, 1 \leq j \leq m\} \\ E(S(n_1, n_2, \dots, n_m)) &= \{v_tv_{t+1}, v_jv_i^j : 1 \leq t \leq m-1, 1 \leq i \leq n_j, 1 \leq j \leq m\}. \end{aligned}$$

We define $f : V(S(n_1, n_2, \dots, n_m)) \rightarrow S$ as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} f(v_1) &= 0, f(v_j) = 2(cT_{j-1} - cT_{j-2} + cT_{j-3} - \dots + (-1)^j cT_1) \text{ for } 2 \leq j \leq m, \\ f(v_i^1) &= 2cT_{m-1+i} \text{ for } 1 \leq i \leq n_1, \\ f(v_i^j) &= 2cT_{m-1+n_1+n_2+\dots+n_{j-1}+i} + (-1)^{j-1}2(cT_1 - cT_2 + cT_3 - \dots + (-1)^j cT_{j-1}) \text{ for } \\ &1 \leq i \leq n_j \text{ and } 2 \leq j \leq m. \end{aligned}$$

For the vertex label f , the induced edge label f^* is defined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} f^*(v_jv_{j+1}) &= cT_j \text{ for } 1 \leq j \leq m-1, \\ f^*(e_i^1) &= cT_{m-1+i} \text{ for } 1 \leq i \leq n_1, \\ f^*(e_i^j) &= cT_{m-1+n_1+n_2+\dots+n_{j-1}+i} \text{ for } 1 \leq j \leq n_j \text{ and } 2 \leq j \leq m. \end{aligned}$$

Then the edge labels are the centered triangular numbers

$$cT_1, cT_2, \dots, cT_{m-1}, cT_m, \dots, cT_{m-1+n_1+n_2, \dots, n_m}$$

and also the vertex labels are different. Hence $S(n_1, n_2, \dots, n_m)$ is a centered triangular mean graph. \square

The centered triangular mean labeling of $S(3, 5, 4, 6)$ is shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6

Theorem 2.6 *The shrub $St(n_1, n_2, \dots, n_m)$ is a centered triangular mean graph.*

Proof let $v_0, v_j, u_i^j (1 \leq j \leq m, 1 \leq i \leq n_j)$ be the vertices of $St(n_1, n_2, \dots, n_m)$. Then $E(St(n_1, n_2, \dots, n_m)) = \{v_0v_j, v_ju_i^j \text{ for } 1 \leq i \leq n_j \text{ and } 1 \leq j \leq m\}$. Define $f : V(St(n_1, n_2, \dots, n_m)) \rightarrow S$ as follows:

$$f(v_0) = 0,$$

$$f(v_j) = 2cT_j \text{ for } 1 \leq j \leq m,$$

$$f(u_i^j) = 2(cT_{m+n_1+n_2+\dots+n_{j-1}+i} - cT_j) \text{ for } 1 \leq i \leq n_j \text{ and } 1 \leq j \leq m.$$

Let $e_i^j = v_ju_i^j$ for $1 \leq i \leq n_j$ and $1 \leq j \leq m$. For each vertex label f , the induced edge label f^* is defined as follows:

$$f^*(v_0v_j) = cT_j \text{ for } 1 \leq j \leq m,$$

$$f^*(e_i^j) = cT_{m+n_1+n_2+\dots+n_{j-1}+i} \text{ for } 1 \leq j \leq m \text{ and } 1 \leq i \leq n_j.$$

Then f is a centered triangular mean labeling of $St(n_1, n_2, \dots, n_m)$. \square

The centered triangular mean labeling of $St(4, 5, 4)$ is shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7

Theorem 2.7 *The banana tree $Bt(\underbrace{n, n, \dots, n}_{m \text{ times}})$ is a centered triangular mean graph.*

Proof Let $v_0, v_j, u_i^j (1 \leq j \leq m, 1 \leq i \leq n)$ be the vertices of $Bt(\underbrace{n, n, \dots, n}_{m \text{ times}})$. Then

$E(\underbrace{Bt(n, n, \dots, n)}_{m \text{ times}}) = \{v_0u_1^j, v_iu_i^j \text{ for } 1 \leq i \leq n \text{ and } 1 \leq j \leq m\}$. Define $f : V(\underbrace{Bt(n, n, \dots, n)}_{m \text{ times}}) \rightarrow S$ as follows:

$$f(v_0) = 0, \quad f(v_j) = 2(cT_{m+j} - cT_j) \quad \text{for } 1 \leq j \leq m,$$

$$f(u_1^j) = 2cT_j \text{ for } 1 \leq j \leq m,$$

$$f(u_i^j) = 2(cT_{2m+(j-1)(n-1)+i-1} - cT_{m+j} + cT_j) \text{ for } 2 \leq i \leq n \text{ and } 1 \leq j \leq m.$$

Let $e_i^j = v_ju_i^j$ for $1 \leq i \leq n$ and $1 \leq j \leq m$. For each vertex label f , the induced edge label f^* is defined as follows:

$$f^*(v_0u_1^j) = cT_j \text{ for } 1 \leq j \leq m,$$

$$f^*(v_ju_1^j) = cT_{m+j} \text{ for } 1 \leq j \leq m,$$

$$f^*(e_i^j) = cT_{2m+(j-1)(n-1)+(i-1)} \text{ for } 1 \leq j \leq m \text{ and } 2 \leq i \leq n.$$

Therefore f is a centered triangular mean labeling of $\underbrace{Bt(n, n, \dots, n)}_{m \text{ times}}$. □

The centered triangular mean labeling of $\underbrace{Bt(3, 3, \dots, 3)}_{8 \text{ times}}$ is shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8

Theorem 2.8 *The graph $P_m @ P_n$ is a centered triangular mean graph.*

proof Let $\{v_j, u_j^i, 1 \leq i \leq n, 1 \leq j \leq m\}$ be the vertices of $P_n @ P_m$ with $v_j = u_j^1, (1 \leq j \leq m)$. Then $E(P_n @ P_m) = \{v_jv_{j+1}, u_j^i u_j^{i+1} : 1 \leq j \leq m - 1, 1 \leq i \leq n - 1\}$. Define $f : V(P_n @ P_m) \rightarrow S$ as follows:

$$f(u_1^1) = 0, \quad f(u_j^1) = 2(cT_{j-1} - cT_{j-2} + cT_{j-3} - \dots + (-1)^j cT_1) \text{ for } 2 \leq j \leq m,$$

$$f(u_1^2) = 2cT_m, \quad f(u_j^2) = 2(cT_{m+j-1} - cT_{j-1} + cT_{j-2} - \dots + (-1)^{j-1}cT_1) \text{ for } 2 \leq j \leq m,$$

$$f(u_j^i) = 2(cT_{(i-1)m+j-1} - cT_{(i-2)m+j-1} + cT_{(i-3)m+j-1} - \dots + (-1)^{i-1}cT_{m+j-1}) + (-1)^{i-1}2(cT_{j-1} - cT_{j-2} + cT_{j-3} - \dots + (-1)^j cT_1)$$

for $1 \leq j \leq m$, $3 \leq i \leq n$. For each vertex label f , the induced edge label f^* is defined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} f^*(v_j v_{j+1}) &= cT_j \text{ for } 1 \leq j \leq m-1, \\ f^*(u_j^1 u_j^2) &= cT_{m+j-1} \text{ for } 1 \leq j \leq m, \\ f^*(u_j^i u_j^{i+1}) &= cT_{mi+j-1} \text{ for } 1 \leq j \leq m \text{ and } 2 \leq i \leq n-1. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore f is a centered triangular labeling of $P_n @ P_m$. □

The centered triangular mean labeling of $P_4 @ P_4$ is shown in Figure 9.

Figure 9

References

[1] David M. Burton, *Elementary Number Theory* (Second Edition), Wm. C. Brown Company Publishers, 1980.
 [2] F. Harary, *Graph Theory*, Addison Wesley, Massachusetts, 1972.
 [3] Joseph A. Gallian, A dynamic survey of graph labeling, *The Electronic Journal of Combinatorics*, #DS6 (2018).
 [4] S. Murugesan, D. Jayaraman and J. Shiama, Centered triangular sum labeling of graphs, *International Journal of Applied Information Systems*, 5(7)(2013), 1-4.
 [5] M. Seenivasan, A. Lourdusamy and M. Raviramasubramanian, Triangular mean labeling of graphs, *Journal of Discrete Mathematical Sciences and Cryptography*, Vol.10(6)(2007), 815-822.
 [6] S. Somasundaram and R. Ponraj, Mean labelings of graphs, *National Academy Science Letter*, 26 (2003), 210-213.